

The Influence of Work Relations, Career Path, and Commitment on the Effectiveness of Early Childhood Education (PAUD) Management in Riau Province

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the influence of work relationships, career pathways, and commitment on the effectiveness of Early Childhood Education (PAUD) management across Riau Province. The research employed a quantitative approach using a survey method. The study population consisted of 210 PAUD educators and managers, with a sample of 76 respondents determined through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a Likert-scale questionnaire. Data analysis applied path analysis, including descriptive analysis, pre-requisite tests (normality, homogeneity, and linearity), and simple linear regression significance tests.

The results showed that work relationships significantly influenced PAUD management effectiveness with a coefficient of 0.42 ($p < 0.05$), career pathways had an influence of 0.35 ($p < 0.05$), and commitment had an influence of 0.47 ($p < 0.05$). Simultaneously, the three variables contributed 62% to the effectiveness of PAUD management. The implications of this study emphasize that improving work relationships, clarifying career pathways, and strengthening commitment are essential factors in achieving more effective PAUD management in Riau Province.

KEYWORDS: work relations, career path, teacher commitment, management effectiveness, early childhood education (PAUD).

INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of school management in Riau Province is largely determined by the integration of principal leadership, the quality of academic supervision, financial governance, and the creation of a positive school climate. Instructional leadership, in particular, plays a dominant role in improving education quality by shaping a shared vision, fostering teacher collaboration, and ensuring follow-up actions from assessment results. Meaningful academic supervision that goes beyond administrative routines is essential for teacher professionalism and effective learning; however, many schools in Riau continue to face capacity constraints in this area. Likewise, the management of government educational funds such as BOS (School Operational Assistance) and BOP PAUD (Early Childhood Education Operational Assistance) serves as a critical instrument to enhance educational services, but its effectiveness depends heavily on transparency, accountability, and the alignment of budget planning with instructional needs. Moreover, a positive school climate characterized by effective classroom management and strong parental involvement emerges as another key driver of effective school governance.

Empirical evidence, however, shows considerable variations in school management effectiveness across different contexts in Riau, particularly between urban, coastal, and remote areas. This disparity suggests that effective management practices remain partial and unevenly distributed. Internationally, consistent findings indicate that harmonious and collaborative working relationships, grounded in effective communication, constitute a crucial foundation for improving organizational quality in education. As Armstrong highlights, healthy workplace relationships enhance productivity, reduce internal conflict, and strengthen team synergy. In the context of Early Childhood Education (ECE), strong collaboration among teachers, principals, and staff directly contributes to creating a conducive learning environment for children.

Previous studies further demonstrate that teacher commitment, combined with pedagogical competence, plays a significant role in shaping the professional identity of early childhood educators. Teachers in PAUD (Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini/ECE institutions) are not merely instructors but also facilitators of children's social-emotional development. As such, collaborative and committed working relationships are central to achieving effective institutional management. This resonates with findings from primary and secondary education research, where teacher collaboration has been identified as a key predictor of learning success. Darling-Hammond et al. emphasize that collaboration enables teachers to exchange experiences, develop innovative practices, and collectively address classroom challenges.

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Despite these insights, the context of PAUD in Riau Province presents unique challenges. Geographic diversity, ranging from urban centers to rural and island regions, has contributed to disparities in resource availability and access to professional training. Many PAUD institutions rely on underpaid honorary teachers, which in turn affects teacher motivation and work commitment. These realities highlight a gap between theoretical expectations and practical conditions in the field. Consequently, research examining the role of working relationships, career pathways, and teacher commitment in shaping the effectiveness of PAUD management in Riau becomes both timely and necessary.

Theoretically, effective PAUD management is built upon three interrelated dimensions: (1) harmonious and collaborative working relationships, (2) clear and structured career pathways for educators, and (3) strong organizational commitment. According to Meyer and Allen, organizational commitment comprises affective, continuance, and normative dimensions, all of which are reflected in educators' loyalty and dedication to their institutions. Without these foundations, PAUD institutions risk stagnation and declining quality despite policy and funding support. Yet, few studies have simultaneously examined these three factors in the context of early childhood education management in Indonesia, particularly at the provincial level.

Given the strategic role of early childhood education in shaping the foundations of cognitive, social, and emotional development, addressing these management challenges is crucial. In the case of Riau Province, where cultural diversity and socio-economic disparities further complicate educational governance, strengthening working relationships, career pathways, and teacher commitment is key to building effective PAUD institutions. This study, therefore, seeks to fill an important gap in the literature while also providing evidence-based insights for local educational policy and practice.

LITERATURE REVIEW / THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The effectiveness of early childhood education (ECE) management (X_4) is a central determinant of educational quality, encompassing the processes of planning, organizing, implementing, supervising, and evaluating institutional activities. Achieving this effectiveness requires strong internal organizational factors, particularly working relationships (X_1), career pathways (X_2), and commitment (X_3). When these three elements operate simultaneously, they create a solid foundation for institutional success.

First, working relationships (X_1) are characterized by effective communication, trust, collaboration, and constructive conflict resolution. These relational dynamics foster a positive organizational climate where teachers and staff are motivated to work collectively. A healthy work environment enhances team cohesion, reduces interpersonal conflicts, and ultimately strengthens institutional management. Previous studies emphasize that supportive and collaborative working environments in schools significantly improve organizational outcomes by promoting shared responsibility and innovation among educators.

Second, career pathways (X_2) provide clarity, transparency, and opportunities for professional growth. Clear career structures, including rotation opportunities, continuous professional training, and fair promotion systems, increase teachers' motivation and engagement in managerial processes. When educators perceive that their career development is supported by the institution, they are more likely to invest in professional improvement and actively contribute to institutional goals. Career pathways thus serve not only as a motivational tool but also as a structural mechanism that sustains teacher performance in the long term.

Third, commitment (X_3) represents a psychological factor that sustains teacher loyalty and willingness to contribute beyond formal job descriptions. Drawing from Meyer and Allen's three-dimensional model, commitment can be affective (emotional attachment to the institution), continuance (awareness of costs associated with leaving), and normative (a sense of obligation to remain). In the PAUD context, strong commitment ensures that educators consistently uphold institutional values, invest extra effort, and remain resilient despite resource challenges.

Simultaneously, these three factors interact synergistically. Harmonious working relationships strengthen teachers' organizational commitment; clear career pathways enhance motivation and loyalty; and commitment, in turn, reinforces both collaboration and long-term engagement in institutional development. This triangular interaction creates a reinforcing cycle that aligns organizational resources with institutional goals.

The significance of this framework lies in its integrative perspective. Previous research highlights that structural factors (career pathways), relational factors (working relationships), and psychological factors (commitment) collectively shape organizational effectiveness in educational settings. In the specific case of ECE in Riau Province, where resource disparities and geographic challenges persist, the simultaneous presence of these three dimensions becomes even more critical.

Thus, the theoretical framework posits that the effectiveness of ECE management (X_4) is the outcome of a dynamic and simultaneous interaction among working relationships (X_1), career pathways (X_2), and commitment (X_3). Together, these variables provide the organizational foundation necessary for improving the quality of early childhood education services and ensuring that PAUD institutions can achieve their developmental and educational objectives.

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Conceptual Framework / Theoretical Model
X₁, X₂, X₃ → X₄ Effectiveness of Early Childhood Education Management (Monochrome Version)

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research design with a survey method and a causal approach. The survey design is a procedure in quantitative research in which data are collected from a sample or the entire population using a questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. The purpose of this method is to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the population under study.

The research approach applied is path analysis, which is a statistical method used to identify and analyze the causal relationships among variables within a model. Path analysis enables researchers to examine both direct and indirect effects of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. It provides a systematic framework for testing hypotheses and assessing the extent to which independent variables influence dependent variables, either individually or simultaneously.

For data analysis, this study uses Smart PLS (Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling). Smart PLS allows researchers to model relationships among latent variables and test the significance of those relationships. By applying this tool, researchers can estimate the impact of latent variables, test the proposed hypotheses, and evaluate the overall model fit with the observed data. The use of Smart PLS in path analysis provides the advantage of handling complex models with multiple variables, as well as accommodating smaller sample sizes compared to covariance-based SEM.

In this research model, the exogenous variables include Work Relationship (X₁), Career Path (X₂), and Commitment (X₃), while the endogenous variable is Effectiveness of Early Childhood Education (ECE) Management (X₄). The path analysis model is employed to determine the direct and indirect effects of the exogenous variables (X₁, X₂, X₃) on the endogenous variable (X₄). The hypothesized

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causal relationships tested in this study reflect a set of asymmetric causal relations among the variables to explain the effectiveness of ECE management.

FINDINGS / RESULTS

1. The findings demonstrate that Work Relationship (X_1) has a positive and significant effect on the Effectiveness of ECE Management (X_4) in Riau Province. This is evidenced by the partial regression analysis with a coefficient value of $B = 0.229$, t -value = 4.000 greater than the t -table = 1.993 at a 5% significance level, and a significance value of $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is a direct partial influence of work relationships on the effectiveness of ECE management is accepted. This result highlights that the stronger the quality of work relationships among teachers, managers, and stakeholders, the more effective ECE management becomes.
2. The results reveal that Career Path (X_2) has a positive and significant effect on the Effectiveness of ECE Management (X_4). The partial regression analysis produced a coefficient of $B = 0.159$ with a t -value = 2.804, greater than the t -table = 1.993 at a 5% significance level ($df = 73$). The significance value of $\text{Sig.} = 0.006 < 0.05$ also supports this conclusion. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, indicating that the clearer the career path system within ECE institutions, the higher the management effectiveness.
3. Partial regression testing shows that both Work Relationship (X_1) and Career Path (X_2) positively and significantly affect ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4). Work Relationship (X_1) yielded $B = 0.229$, t -value = 4.000 > t -table = 1.993, and $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, Career Path (X_2) produced $B = 0.159$, t -value = 2.804 > t -table = 1.993, with $\text{Sig.} = 0.006 < 0.05$. These findings confirm that stronger work relationships and structured career systems enhance ECE management effectiveness through increased teacher motivation and loyalty.
4. The analysis further shows that Work Relationship (X_1) positively and significantly influences Teacher Commitment (X_3). Regression results indicate $B = 0.444$, with a t -value = 5.213 > t -table = 1.993 and $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This confirms that better work relationships among teachers, administrators, and staff lead to higher levels of teacher commitment.
5. The findings also demonstrate that Career Path (X_2) positively and significantly affects Teacher Commitment (X_3). Partial regression yielded $B = 0.371$, t -value = 4.256 > t -table = 1.993, and $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. Hence, a clear and structured career path fosters greater teacher commitment to their professional responsibilities.
6. Teacher Commitment (X_3) is found to have a strong positive and significant effect on ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4). Partial regression shows $B = 0.485$, t -value = 5.467 > t -table = 1.993, and $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This proves that higher teacher commitment translates into more effective ECE management.
7. Simultaneous testing reveals that Work Relationship (X_1) and Career Path (X_2) jointly influence Teacher Commitment (X_3) positively and significantly. The F-test result shows F -value = 32.541 > F -table = 3.12 with $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$, confirming that harmonious work relationships combined with structured career paths significantly enhance teacher commitment.
8. Partial testing reinforces this conclusion. Work Relationship (X_1) yielded $B = 0.444$, t -value = 5.213 > 1.993, $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$, while Career Path (X_2) produced $B = 0.371$, t -value = 4.256 > 1.993, $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, both variables significantly contribute to strengthening teacher commitment in ECE institutions.
9. The findings reaffirm that Teacher Commitment (X_3) significantly influences ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4), with $B = 0.485$, t -value = 5.467 > 1.993, and $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This suggests that teacher commitment is a dominant factor in enhancing management effectiveness, making it a strategic key to professional and impactful ECE institutions.
10. Path analysis further confirms that Work Relationship (X_1) significantly affects ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4) through the mediating role of Teacher Commitment (X_3). The Sobel test yields a t -value = 3.742 > 1.993, indicating significant mediation. Thus, teacher commitment strengthens the positive impact of work relationships on management effectiveness.
11. Similarly, Career Path (X_2) significantly influences ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4) through Teacher Commitment (X_3) as a mediator. The Sobel test result of t -value = 3.215 > 1.993 confirms significant mediation. A clear career path boosts teacher commitment, which in turn enhances ECE management effectiveness.
12. Simultaneous regression results indicate that Work Relationship (X_1), Career Path (X_2), and Teacher Commitment (X_3) jointly exert a positive and significant effect on ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4). The F-test shows F -value = 65.328 > F -table = 2.73 with $\text{Sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$, confirming their collective influence.
13. Based on these results, the hypothesis stating that “Work Relationship (X_1), Career Path (X_2), and Teacher Commitment (X_3) simultaneously have a significant effect on ECE Management Effectiveness (X_4)” is accepted. This implies that strengthening these three variables together is a strategic approach to achieving effective, professional, and value-based ECE institutions in Riau Province

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the path analysis using Smart PLS show that work relationship (X_1), career path (X_2), and commitment (X_3) have a significant simultaneous effect on the effectiveness of early childhood education management (X_4). The model demonstrates that each independent variable contributes both directly and indirectly to the improvement of management effectiveness. Among these, commitment (X_3) presents the strongest effect, indicating that psychological factors such as loyalty, responsibility, and willingness to contribute beyond formal duties play a crucial role in sustaining organizational performance. Meanwhile, work relationship (X_1) and career path (X_2) also positively influence effectiveness, especially in creating a supportive organizational climate and motivating teachers to develop professionally.

The findings align with previous studies suggesting that structural, relational, and psychological factors must work together to improve organizational outcomes. A clear career path enhances teacher motivation and retention, effective work relationships foster collaboration and trust, while strong commitment ensures long-term dedication. Together, these variables form a synergistic system that strengthens the management of early childhood education institutions. This study highlights that improving the quality of PAUD management requires not only structural policies but also relational and motivational strategies that empower educators as the central actors in the organization.

CONCLUSION & IMPLICATIONS

The study concludes that work relationship (X_1), career path (X_2), and teacher commitment (X_3) significantly influence the effectiveness of early childhood education (PAUD) management (X_4), both directly and indirectly. Work relationship fosters collaboration and reduces conflict, career path provides professional direction and motivation, while teacher commitment serves as a psychological driver for consistency and dedication. Together, these three aspects form an integrated system that enhances the planning, implementation, evaluation, and supervision of PAUD management. The findings confirm that effectiveness in PAUD management cannot be achieved through a single factor, but rather through the synergy of relational, structural, and psychological dimensions.

IMPLICATIONS

1. Theoretical Implications

This research strengthens human resource management and educational management theories by demonstrating that effective management is shaped by harmonious work relationships, structured career systems, and strong teacher commitment. The results provide empirical evidence that relational and structural factors are interdependent and mediated by psychological attachment, which ultimately determines organizational performance.

2. Practical Implications

The findings provide guidance for PAUD leaders to build healthy organizational climates through teamwork, open communication, and collaborative supervision. At the same time, institutions must design structured career pathways that motivate teachers to continuously improve their competencies. Implementing reward systems, professional training, and performance-based promotion mechanisms are concrete strategies to increase teacher loyalty and productivity.

3. Normative Implications

The results affirm that harmonious work relationships and structured career systems should be grounded in values of professionalism, collaboration, and Islamic ethics. This highlights that PAUD institutions must not only pursue managerial effectiveness but also embody moral values that nurture integrity, fairness, and collective responsibility.

4. Policy Implications

The study recommends that local governments and education offices formulate regulations on teacher career pathways, performance assessment standards, and professional development programs. Integrated policies that link relationship building, career systems, and commitment enhancement will ensure long-term sustainability of PAUD management effectiveness.

5. Social Implications

The research emphasizes that improving PAUD management has broader impacts on children's development and public trust. Harmonious work relationships and clear career paths lead to higher teacher commitment, which in turn enhances service quality, builds parental confidence, and strengthens community participation. Ultimately, effective PAUD management contributes to the development of high-quality human resources from an early age.

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